

An Overview of Flood Disaster, its Impacts on Education and Healthcare Deliveries in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines flood disaster, its impacts on education and healthcare deliveries in Kano State. Flood is among the most devastating natural disasters in Kano State, claiming lives and causing more damage to education and healthcare sectors than any other natural phenomena. Prolonged rainfall events are the most common causes of flooding in the state. These events are usually associated with several days, weeks or months long of continuous rainfall. Flooding disrupts the schooling of children and the delivery of education in the state, even in non-major floods, parents are not keen to send their children to school as they fear them treading dangerous flood waters en route to schools. Similarly, flooding has both direct and indirect impacts on health sector. Increased deaths and injury are direct effects of flooding having occurred in various parts of the state. Kano state's fledgling health sector suffers setbacks from annual flooding disasters. Water-borne life-threatening disease epidemics like Typhoid, Cholera, and Dysentery are common during flooding. In a nutshell, floods provide a perfect breeding ground for parasites like mosquitoes which leads to a rise in the incidence of parasite borne diseases like Malaria. The paper concludes that, unless the causal factors of flooding are adequately controlled, the disaster would continue to impede educational and healthcare deliveries in Kano state. A major recommendation offered suggests that government should construct viable and quality drainage system in flood prone areas and around educational and healthcare facilities in the state in order to enable easy access and delivery of services.

Keywords: Flood Disaster, Flood's Impacts, Education and Healthcare Deliveries

Introduction

Flood disaster occur as a result of excess water flowing on land that used to be dry (Adeniji, 2018). Among natural disasters, floods have been reported to be responsible for almost half of casualties (Aderogba, 2012). Floods are also the most frequent Environmental disasters (natural disasters), affecting over 2.8 billion people in the world and causing over 200,000 deaths over the past three decades (Agbonkheshe, et.al. 2014). Between 1995 and 2015, the lives of 2.3 billion people were affected, making floods accountable for 47% of all weather-related disasters globally (Aja & Olaore, 2014). Factors that cause flood events are complicated and interrelated (Akinloye, 2018). Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa experienced one of its largest flood disasters in 2012 (Aifesehi 2013; Raimi et.al. 2018) causing the

destruction of assets worth over US\$9.5 billion, most of which were in the urban centres (Federal Government of Nigeria [FGN], 2013).

In Kano state however, the environmental impact of floods on both individuals and communities cannot be overemphasized because of its social, economic, and psychological implications. For instance, in 2013 about 500 persons were displaced by flood in some Local Government Areas (LGA) of the state. In the same incidence, the State's agency for flood management also claimed that over 100 houses were destroyed across the LGAs (<http://floodlist.com/africa/kano-nigeria>). In another disaster that took place in 2018, the State Environmental Management Agency (SEMA) reported that flood destroyed over 40 houses and killed one person in Danbatta LGA of Kano state

(<https://punchng.com/flood-kills-one-destroys-40-houses-in-kano/>). Similarly, News Agency of Nigeria in Raimi et.al (2018) disclosed that 31 persons were killed and 10,000 houses were destroyed by flood in Kano state. THISDAY (2020) reported that 3,954 residents were displaced in seven LGAs; towns and villages were cut-off from their respective LGA headquarters. These LGAs are Rimingado, Tofa, Danbatta, Kunbotso, Rogo, Ungogo and Bunkure (<https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2020/07/20/floods-destroy-bridges-in-kano/>). In another revelation, SEMA gave a figure of 5,200 houses and four deaths as the casualties of the year 2020 flood disaster in Kano state.

Flooding disrupts the schooling of children and the delivery of education in many ways, no matter the severity of the flooding. Even in non-major floods, parents are not keen to send their children to school due to flood. Health sector suffers setbacks from annual flooding disasters. Water-borne life-threatening disease epidemics like Typhoid, Cholera, and Dysentery are common during flooding (Okaka and Odhiambo 2018; Rieckmann et al. 2018). Floods provide a perfect breeding ground for parasites like mosquitoes which leads to a rise in the incidence of parasite borne diseases like Malaria.

The thrust of this paper is to overview the environmental impacts of flood disaster in Nigeria with specific focus on education and healthcare deliveries.

Conceptualization of Flood Disaster

Flood is among the most devastating natural Disasters in the world, claiming more lives and causing more property damage than any other natural phenomena. In Nigeria, at least 20 per cent of the population and eight per cent of its industries are at risk from one form of flooding or another. This includes the whole spectrum from the rich urban residents of Victoria Island, Lagos, Sharada industrial layout in Kano, Eleme industrial layout in Port Harcourt etc. to poor farmers and fishermen in Benue and Niger trough and the coastal regions of Nigeria (NEMA, 2006).

This phenomenon called flood occurs when water covers previously dry areas, i.e., when large amounts of water flow from a source such as a river or a broken pipe onto a previously dry area, or when water overflows banks or barriers (Flood Protection, 2012). Floods can be environmentally important to local ecosystems. For example, some river floods bring nutrients to soil such as in Egypt where the annual flooding of the Nile River carries nutrients to otherwise dry land. Floods can also have an economic

and emotional impact on people, particularly if their property is directly affected. Having a better understanding of what causes flooding can help people to be better prepared and to perhaps minimize or prevent flood damage (Rufat et.al. 2015).

During flooding, timely and detailed situation reports are required by authorities to locate and identify the affected areas and to implement corresponding damage mitigations. During this period of response or relief, it is essential that information be accurate and timely in order to address emergency situations like search, rescue and relief. Space information can help to augment ground information for real-time damage assessment and extending threat to life and property. Space imagery integrated with GIS can also help in preparing flood recovery plans. Information collected on the mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery phases can be integrated into master flood prevention projects (Oladokun and Ishola, 2010).

Risk of catastrophic losses due to flooding is significant given deforestation and the increasing proximity of large populations to coastal areas, river basins and lakeshores. Considering the global picture of flood disaster, the various rolling Vulnerability Assessments conducted in different countries indicate that the last two decades have seen an increase in the frequency and occurrence of climate-induced flood (Rieckmann et.al. 2018).

Causes of flooding in Kano State

The most common causes of flood disaster in Kano state are climate related, most especially rainfall. Prolonged rainfall events are the most common cause of flooding in the state. These events are usually associated with several days, weeks or months long of continuous rainfall. Human impacts on river catchments influence flood behaviour (Richard Samans et.al. 2017). Land use changes in particular have a direct impact on the magnitude and behaviour of floods in the state. Deforestation results in increased run-off and often a decrease in channel capacity due to increased sedimentation rates (Reed & Mberu, 2014).

While climate change has led to more rains than in the past which has increased the incidence of flooding, Kano state's flooding is mostly human induced and exacerbated by human-nature interactions (Aderogba 2012). The human-nature interactions that cause flooding form the focus of this paper and include, but are not limited to:

1. Poor or non-existent drainage systems

This is a major human-induced exacerbator of the flooding experienced in many states of Nigeria including Kano (Ogundele & Jegede 2011). Most

residential areas in Kano state have no drainage system and rely on natural drainage channels, and it is common for buildings and other infrastructure to be constructed in a manner that actually obstructs these drainage channels which results in flooding during the rainy season (Nabegu 2014). Nigeria's increasing urbanization has seen a growing proportion of ground surfaces concreted, which means there is no percolation of water, and adequate drains are not in place to take care of the surface runoff (Adeloye & Rustum 2011). The lack of provision for drainage is one of the main causes of flooding in Kano state. There is a pressing need to construct drainage systems to tackle the flooding problem (Etuonovbe 2011).

2. Poor waste management system

Poor waste management is one of the anthropogenic factors contributing to, and worsening the already difficult flooding problem in many states of Nigeria (Ojo and Adejgbagbe 2017). The poor attitude of Nigerians to waste disposal has been widely discussed in various studies (Eneji et al. 2016; Ojo and Adejgbagbe 2017; Olukanni, Adebayo, and Tenebe 2014; Sridhar and Ojediran 1983). Drainage blockages linked to poor sanitation practices are common in Nigeria's highly populated urban areas. Roadside dumping, canal dumping, and dumping in rains is commonly practiced among a large proportion of the residents in Kano state. This causes blockage and results in flooding during the rainy season (Onwuemele 2012).

3. Unregulated urbanization

Flooding and urbanization are intricately related in both developing and developed countries. Over 50% of Nigerians live in urban areas today (Farrell 2018). Kano state is witnessing high urbanization rates without commensurate provision of urban infrastructure and amenities (Aderogba 2012). Agricultural lands are also being increasingly converted to residential areas to accommodate housing needs and development is carried out without proper controls and infrastructure in place, thus worsening the flooding problem (Dan-Jumbo, Metzger, & Clark 2018). Urban planning in Kano state is poor and this is compounded by numerous compliance problems; this poor planning is a primary cause of the flooding being experienced in across the state. Flooding in Kano is therefore inextricably linked to poor urban development practices (Omoboye and Festus 2014).

4. Weak implementation of planning laws and corruption

Nigeria's current planning laws are standard but their development and implementation are poorly controlled (Nnaemeka-Okeke 2016). Political

interference in planning work, understaffing and a lack of working equipment are factors that negatively impact effective planning and the execution of duties by the planners (Nnaemeka-Okeke 2016; Oluwaseyi 2019). The lax implementation of planning laws mean construction projects on natural floodplains and storm water paths are approved, which exacerbates the flooding problem and impacts on sustainability. Corruption is also a factor. It is not uncommon for town planning officials to accept bribes and overlook issues – these may include the unauthorized use of land, the alteration of approved construction plans in areas that obstruct drains and natural waterways, sub-standard construction of infrastructure like bridges which subsequently collapse during the rains (Oladokun and Proverbs 2016). Resulting debris reduces the carrying capacity of the channels which induces flooding and worsens the problem originally being addressed. The people also capitalize on the loophole of ineffective development control and a lot of times extend their buildings over the approved areas and in some cases go as far as building over drainages. This non-implementation of the laws is inimical to achieving sustainable urban development. Lax planning and the lack of valid building approvals are the root cause of irresponsible developments with attendant consequences (Adeloye and Rustum 2011).

Impact of Flooding on Quality Education delivery in Kano State

The role and importance of education in achieving sustainable development cannot be overstated (Oghenekohwo & Frank-Oputu 2017). In the developing world, there is even more need to promote education as the literacy levels fall well below that of the developed world (Winthrop & McGivney 2015). To that effect, there are numerous campaigns to promote universal basic education for all, especially for young children, but flooding disasters undermine this right to education of children in many communities in Kano state (Mudavanhu 2014). Displacements due to flooding cause children in disaster areas to become educationally disadvantaged at the crucial school age, which sets them up for continued economic disadvantage and opportunities later in life. There is evidence of overall poorer educational performances and outcomes, reduced level of educational levels, and general disadvantages that continue into adulthood (Erica, Jessie, & Stephanie 2018).

Flooding disrupts the schooling of children and the delivery of education in Kano state, no matter the severity of the flooding. Even in non-major floods,

parents are not keen to send their children to school as they fear them treading dangerous flood waters en route to schools. They cannot ascertain if storms or rainfall will increase the severity of floods when the children are away at school and so prefer to have them at home where they have greater control over their safety, should the severity of flooding increase or there be need of evacuation. The teachers are also not in the best psychological state to teach because they also have to handle terrible conditions either in the school, home, or emergency shelter to get their lesson notes ready. They also have to deal with their own flooded homes and damaged properties. Parents on their part cannot do much for their children's education at this period or help with teaching on the home front. Educational materials are destroyed and even after the floods recede or the waters dry up, longer term effects in the education system are experienced because it is not easy to replace damaged educational materials especially in developing countries. In places prone to annual flooding, there might also be reluctance on the part of the authorities to replace these learning materials, knowing that it may be damaged again during the next flooding cycle.

In Nigeria, schools serve as emergency shelters during disasters like flooding, so they cannot serve their primary educational purpose. The effects of flooding disasters in the education sector become more damaging in places where access to education is already inadequate. There are usually delayed reconstruction efforts for damaged schools in the worst hit developing nations. The effect of flooding on the education of young school children is much more profound in the areas that experience annual flooding of such a scale that is not classified as a major disaster, meaning that these children lose many months of school year every year. Also, disasters like flood bring severe hardship to poor families who might be forced to withdraw their children totally from school and push them into the labor market to work to help provide for their families basic needs which brings a halt to their formal education (Kousky 2016).

Impact of Flooding on Healthcare Delivery in Kano State

Flooding has both direct and indirect impacts on health. Increased deaths and injury are direct effects of flooding with 90% of these direct effects having occurred in developing countries like Nigeria (Zorn 2018). Kano state's fledgling health sector suffers setbacks from annual flooding disasters. Water-borne life-threatening disease epidemics like Typhoid, Cholera, and Dysentery are common during flooding (Okaka & Odhiambo 2018; Rieckmann et

al. 2018). Floods provide a perfect breeding ground for parasites like mosquitoes which leads to a rise in the incidence of parasite borne diseases like Malaria. Women and children are especially vulnerable to these diseases which can lead to death. Flooded homes provide a good damp environment for mildews and molds to grow sporadically which triggers upper respiratory illnesses for people who have allergies and episodes for asthma patients. Such health problems mostly affect the elderly and children. Power outages post-floods in developed countries force people to resort to fossil fuel-powered generators. When the generators are run without adequate ventilation, deaths due to Carbon Monoxide (CO) poisoning can occur (Prevention 2017). Even after floodwaters recede, health risks and threats remain. For example, when electrical wires become immersed in water, there is increased risk of electric shock. Debris like twigs, woods, broken tiles, falling walls, and weakened structures can cause physical injury.

Pollutants like insecticides and pesticides, animal, and human feces, sewage, fertilizers, and other contaminants are rife in floodwaters which also carry disease causing micro-organisms (Oriji 2015). Contact of contaminated waters with agricultural crops and food items elsewhere makes food unsafe for human and animal consumption. Power outages are common during flooding disasters and this affects food stored in the home and may cause serious health threats (DFTE 2017). During floods in many states of Nigeria, water sources become polluted. The ground becomes waterlogged and wastewater and sewage treatment plants become overburdened with the contaminated floodwaters causing backflow into homes and lower lying surroundings. Private septic tanks and wells are common in Kano and become overfilled with polluted water during flooding and become a harbinger of diseases and infections.

Physical and emotional trauma are triggered by floods (Alderman, Turner, & Tong 2012). Tong (2017) highlighted the numerous ways mental health is affected by flooding events. Tong cites studies that show increased stress-related and mental health illnesses like post-traumatic stress disorders, anxiety, depression, and even behavioral shifts like aggression, sleeplessness, anger, hyperactivity, and suicide among flood victims. Long-term psychological distress, even years after flooding, is very common (Rufat et al. 2015).

Conclusion

Literature on flood disaster has shown the etiology of flooding and its attending impacts on education and healthcare deliveries in Kano state.

Causes of flooding in the state range from lack of quality drainage system to non-implementation of planning laws and corruption. So long as these causal factors are left uncontrolled, flood is expected to increase substantially in coming years as a result of both climate change and continued socio-economic development. Further, it is clear that most flood studies acknowledge its negative impacts on people and the environment especially in the areas of education and healthcare deliveries, however, most of the studies on impacts of flood were domiciled in South-East, South-South and South-West of Nigeria. The very few of the related literature in Northern Nigeria examined the flood prevalence in North-Central states. No doubt, figures of impacts due to floods in Kano state abound, they were nevertheless centered on physical damages to lives and property. This paper is therefore an attempt at unveiling flood's impacts on education and healthcare deliveries in Kano state.

Recommendations

1. Government should construct viable and quality drainage system in flood prone areas and around educational and healthcare facilities in the state in order to enable easy access and delivery of services.
2. Government should develop waste management system and encourage residents to make good use of the facilities.
3. Government should ensure effective regulation of urbanization by providing urban infrastructure and amenities.
4. Government should implement planning laws and ensure that construction of all sort of structures are devoid of corruption.

References

- Adelekan, I. O. (2016). Flood Risk Management in the Coastal City of Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Flood Risk Management* 9 (3): 255–264. doi:10.1111/jfr3.12179.
- Adeniji, O. A. (2018). Climate Change and Environmental Impacts of Flood in Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science* 8 (8), 10-16.
- Aderogba, K. A. (2012). Qualitative Studies of Recent Floods and Sustainable Growth and Development of Cities and Towns in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences* 1 (3), 1.
- Agbonkhese, O., Agbonkhese, E., Aka, E., Joe-Abaya, J., Ocholi, M. & Adekunle, A. (2014). Flood Menace in Nigeria: Impacts, Remedial and

Management Strategies. *Civil and Environmental Research* 6 (4), 32–40.

- Aja, G. N., & Olaore, A. Y. (2014). The Impact of Flooding on the Social Determinants of Health in Nigeria: A Case for North-South Institutional Collaboration to Address Climate Issues." *Developing Country Studies* 4 (22), 6–12.
- Akinloye, I. A. (2018). Towards the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria: Maximizing the Influence of Religious Leaders. *Stellenbosch Theological Journal* 4 (1), 39–60.
- Akukwe, T., Krhoda, G. & Oluoko-Odingo, A. (2018). Principal Component Analysis of the Effects of Flooding on Food Security in Agrarian Communities of South Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2 (2), 205–212.
- Bubeck, P., Kreibich, H., Penning-Rowsell, E. C., Botzen, W., de Moel, H., & Klijn, F. (2017). Explaining Differences in Flood Management Approaches in Europe and in the USA—a Comparative Analysis. *Journal of Flood Risk Management* 10 (4) 436–445. doi:10.1111/jfr3.12151.
- Chukwu, O. G., Wekpe, V., & Ikebude, C. (2018). Impact of Coastal Flooding on Fish Production in Brass, Niger Delta Nigeria, Implication for Coastal Resource Management. *Oceanography and Fisheries* 6 (1). doi:10.19080/OFOAJ.2018.06.555678.
- FGN. (2013). Nigeria Post-disaster Needs Assessment. *A Report by the Federal Government of Nigeria, with Technical Support from the European Union, United Nation, World Bank, and other Partners, Nigeria Post-Disaster Need Assessment 2012*, 154.
- Kousky, C. (2016). Impacts of Natural Disasters on Children. *The Future of Children* 26(1): 73–92.
- Kwari, J. W., Paul, M. K., & Shekarau, L. B. (2015). The Impacts of Flooding on Socio-Economic Development and Agriculture in Northern Nigeria: A Case Study of 2012 Flooding in Yola and Numan Areas of Adamawa State Nigeria." *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 6 (7). doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.34970.54725.
- Mwape, Y. P. (2009). *An Impact of Floods on the Socio-economic Livelihoods of People: A Case Study of Sikaunzwe Community in Kazungula District of Zambia*. Bloemfontein: University of the Free State.
- National Population Commission [NPC] (2020). Nigeria Population Estimate as at 2020.

- Nnaemeka-Okeke, R. (2016). "Urban Sprawl and Sustainable City Development in Nigeria." *Journal of Ecological Engineering* 17 (2): 1-11.
- OCHA. (2012). "Nigeria: Floods Situation Report No. 2". Nigeria . https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Full%20Report_1141.pdf.
- Ogundele, J, & Jegede, A. O. (2011). "Environmental Influences of Flooding on Urban Growth and Development of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria." *Studies in Sociology of Science* 2 (2): 89.
- Ojo, O. O. & Adejugbagbe, J. A. (2017). "Solid Waste Disposal Attitude in Sango Ota, Ogun State: Implication for Sustainable City Development in Nigeria." *Journal of Environment and Waste Management* 4 (3): 253–260.
- Okaka, F. O. & Odhiambo, B. (2018). "Relationship between Flooding and Out Break of Infectious Diseases in Kenya: A Review of the Literature." *Journal of Environmental and Public Health* 2018: 1–8. doi:10.1155/2018/5452938.
- Olanrewaju, C. C. M. Chitakira, O. A. Olanrewaju, & Louw. E. (2019). "Impacts of Flood Disasters in Nigeria: A Critical Evaluation of Health Implications and Management." *Jàmbá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies* 11 (1): 1–9.
- Oluwaseyi, O. B. (2019). "Assessment of Physical Planning Administration in Nigeria."
- Raimi, M. , O. T. Vivien, O. E. Odipe, & O. E. Owobi . (2018). "The Sources of Water Supply, Sanitation Facilities and Hygiene Practices in Oil Producing Communities in Central Senatorial District of Bayelsa State, Nigeria." *Med Crave Online Journal of Public Health* 7 (6): 337–345.
- Ran, J. & Nedovic-Budic, Z. (2016). "Integrating Spatial Planning and Flood Risk Management: A New Conceptual Framework for the Spatially Integrated Policy Infrastructure." *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 57: 68–79. doi:10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2016.01.008.
- Rieckmann, A. , C. C. Tamason, E. S. Gurley, N. H. Rod, & P. K. M.Jensen . (2018). "Exploring Droughts and Floods and Their Association with Cholera Outbreaks in sub-Saharan Africa: A Register-based Ecological Study from 1990 to 2010." *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 98 (5): 1269–1274. doi:10.4269/ajtmh.17-0778.
- Schanze, J. (2006). "Flood Risk Management—a Basic Framework." In *Flood Risk Management: Hazards, Vulnerability and Mitigation Measures*, 1–20. Netherlands: Springer.